

Dynamic Stress Concentrations in Some Composite Strips with a Circular Hole under High-Velocity Tension

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ABSTRACT

Dynamic stress concentrations under high-velocity tensile loading conditions are investigated for composite strips with a central circular hole. Photoelastic coating technique is utilized with a newly-constructed 9-frame high-speed Cranz-Schardin camera of reflection type. The excellent reflective plane is the key point to obtain clear isochromatic fringe patterns. Four different kinds of composites in a very wide range of anisotropy are tested to study the effects of anisotropy, loading direction and the (hole diameter/strip width) ratio on the dynamic stress distribution. Dynamic stress and strain distribution around a hole is found to vary remarkably with the change in anisotropy of each composite. In some tests, dynamic fractures caused by stress concentrations are also photographed. Photoelastic-coating results are then compared with the results obtained by strain-gage experiments and finite-element analysis, to ensure the validity of the present dynamic photoelastic-coating analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Dynamic photoelasticity has been developed to study dynamic problems in isotropic materials such as wave propagation, dynamic crack propagation and dynamic stress concentrations around notches or holes (for example, see Refs.(1, 2)). There has been much progress in transparent model materials and in high-speed photography. However, the corresponding dynamic problems in anisotropic materials, especially in composites, have remained to be investigated. There have been many attempts in anisotropic photoelasticity utilizing transparent glass fiber composites (for example, see Refs.(3, 4)). But it is difficult to make a transparent model of high fiber-volume fraction and almost impossible to make a model for a unidirectional carbon fiber composite.

Dynamic photoelastic-coating technique is useful for this purpose. The authors devise a new Cranz-Schardin camera of reflection type to obtain clear high-speed photographs and make efforts to obtain a highly-reflective surface at the back of the photoelastic coating. With this experimental device developed, dynamic stress or strain concentrations around a circular hole in some typical composite strips are investigated under high-velocity tensile loadings. With four different kinds of composites, the effects of anisotropy, loading direction and the (hole diameter/strip width) ratio on the dynamic stress (strain) distributions are examined. Then the analyzed results of this photoelastic-coating

experiment are compared with the results obtained by strain-gage measurements and FEM analysis.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Since the details of experimental methods are given in Refs.(5, 6), a brief summary is described. A Cranz-Schardin camera of reflection type was designed by the authors and is comprised of three basic subsystems which include: the light-source assembly, the multiple-frame camera, and the delay generator. The arrangement of the optical system is shown in Fig. 1, where the test specimen (Fig. 2) is used as a reflective plane. The light-source assembly contains a square array of 9 xenon flash tubes which produce short (0.7-2.1 microseconds) intense flash of light. A filter with a sufficiently narrow band of $470-490 \times 10^{-9}$ meters was employed in front of each flash tube to obtain monochromatic light. In addition, a small lens was also equipped in front of each filter to increase the light on the surface of the photoelastic coating. Each flash was activated at least every 10 μ s in the present experiments. The field lens collects the light from flash tubes and focuses it on camera lenses. The multiple-frame camera contains 9 camera lenses and 9 distinct images can be separated by the geometric positioning shown in Fig. 1. Both the light-source assembly and the 9-frame camera are fixed on the beds which are triaxially movable to facilitate the positioning of the images.

Photoelastic coatings used in the present experiments should have highly reflective backings and the high bond strength between coatings and composites. Through some trials and errors, the following technique was adopted for fabricating a photoelastic-coating specimen with a central circular hole. A circular hole with a diameter of D was drilled in an epoxy photoelastic coating and pure aluminum was vacuum-deposited on it as uniformly as possible. The fabricated coating was then bonded with the same type of epoxy adhesive to a composite specimen with a circular hole drilled by a diamond drill whose diameter was D. A Teflon circular disk whose diameter was slightly smaller than D was used to adjust the position of holes. Mechanical properties of the photoelastic coating were determined by the combination of strain-gage experiments and ultrasonic-wave velocity measurements. Young's modulus E_c and Poisson's ratio ν_c are:

$$E_c = 338 \text{ kg/mm}^2, \nu_c = 0.40 \quad (1)$$

Although these are quasi-static values, these values for epoxy resin with relatively high Young's modulus are considered to be almost the same under the deformation rates of the present dynamic-tension experiments.

Dynamic tensile loading was accomplished by dropping a 20-kilogram weight along a weight guide on a 425-gram impact block fixed to the lower end of the composite specimen. The velocity of the impact block, v , amounted to 5.4 m/s. Since the upper end of the specimen was attached to the specimen guide with a adhesive tape just enough to support the specimen weight, the upper end can be assumed to be free. The contact of the falling weight and the impact block was used to trigger the delay generator of the camera assembly and the transient-wave digital memory for recording dynamic strains. In every test, an incident strain was measured by a strain gage near the impact block and the recorded strain was reproducible. At the end of the horizontal diameter of the hole (denoted by subscript B), the strain was measured as the average of two strain-gage recordings.

DYNAMIC PHOTOELASTIC-COATING TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A list of dynamic photoelastic-coating tests is shown in Table 1. Four different kinds of composites, glass/polyester plain-woven cloth (denoted by G/P, PW), glass/polyester semi-unidirectional satin-woven cloth (G/P, SUSW), glass/polyester, unidirectional (G/P, UD), and carbon/epoxy, unidirectional (C/E, UD) were tested. The effects of anisotropy, angle ϕ between fibers and the loading direction, and the (hole diameter/specimen width) ratio, D/W, were investigated (5). Only representative examples are presented here.

Glass/Polyester, Unidirectional, D/W = 26/50, $\phi = 0^\circ$

Typical strain-gage records are shown in Fig. 3. After a rise time of approximately 70 μ s, the incident strain reaches the constant value ϵ_0 , which is close to the calculated value $\epsilon_{0\text{cal}} = v/c_L$, where c_L is the longitudinal-wave speed in a bar and v is the impact-block speed. A sequence of high-speed isochromatic-fringe patterns in the photoelastic coating is shown in Fig. 4. The time shown starts when the head of the incident strain reaches the center of the hole. Time-dependent two-dimensional strain concentration around the hole can be seen clearly enough to analyze. In the earlier stage, the maximum fringe value on the hole boundary exists upstream from the hole center but moves gradually to the end of the horizontal diameter. As the incident strain reaches its constant value ϵ_0 , fringe patterns become symmetric with respect to the horizontal diameter and similar to static fringe patterns obtained in Ref. (7).

The interpretation of these isochromatic fringes and discussions of the applicability of photoelastic-coating methods to composites can be found in Refs. (7-9). The applicability of the methods under high-velocity deformation is examined here through the comparison of the results of photoelastic-coating, strain-gage experiments and FEM numerical analysis. Strains in the coating are related to the fringe order N by,

$$\epsilon_1^C - \epsilon_2^C = N \cdot \frac{\lambda}{2t_C K} = N \cdot F \quad (2)$$

where $(\epsilon_1^C - \epsilon_2^C)$ and t_C are the difference in the principal strains and the thickness of the coating, λ is the wavelength of the monochromatic light, K is the sensitivity constant of the coating, and F is the coating fringe value in terms of strain. In the present experiment, $\lambda = 480 \times 10^{-9}$ m, $t_C = 1.01$ mm, and $K = 0.128$ (dynamically calibrated), therefore $F = 1856 \times 10^{-6}$ /fringe. To determine the strains in the specimen, usually the strains in the coating are assumed to be transmitted from the specimen without loss, then, using a subscript s denoting specimen,

$$\epsilon_1^C - \epsilon_2^C = \epsilon_1^S - \epsilon_2^S = N \cdot F \quad (3)$$

The transient fringe patterns corresponding to Fig. 4 were numerically calculated using a two-dimensional FEM, where Eq. (3) was assumed and are shown in Fig. 5. Static elastic constants shown in Fig. 4 were assumed in the calculation. Constant-strain triangular elements were used in the analysis with 488 nodal points and 846 elements and the transient matrix equation was integrated numerically by the Newmark generalized-acceleration method. Initial velocities at nodal points upstream from the hole were assumed to reduce possible accumulated errors. The details of the FEM analysis can be found in Ref. (5). Similarity of experimental and FEM transient fringe patterns at each corresponding time ensures the applicability of the present dynamic photoelastic-coating analysis.

The assumption given by Eq. (3) can be erroneous particularly on hole boundaries. The effect of Poisson's ratio mismatch between the coating and the specimen is pronounced on the hole boundary, where a distortion of the displacement field occurs through the thickness of the coating. At least at the end of the horizontal diameter of the hole, the strain ϵ_B can be evaluated as (7, 8):

$$\frac{NF}{1+v^C} < \epsilon_B = \epsilon_1^C = \epsilon_1^S < \frac{NF}{1+v_L^S} \quad (4)$$

assuming $v^C > v_L^S$. Then the strain concentration factor K defined by ϵ_B/ϵ_0 , which is also the stress concentration factor, σ_B/σ_0 ($\sigma_B = E_L \epsilon_B$, $\sigma_0 = E_L \epsilon_0$) in this case, is,

$$K_C = \frac{NF}{\epsilon_0(1+v^C)} < K < \frac{NF}{\epsilon_0(1+v_L^S)} = K_S \quad (v^C > v_L^S) \quad (5)$$

Figure 6 shows a comparison of transient strain (stress) concentration factors obtained by photoelastic-coating methods, strain-gage measurements, and FEM analysis. The position and direction of gages adhered incorrectly and difficulty in reading fine fringe orders might introduce some errors in the experiments.

However, all the dynamic concentration factors increase gradually to approach the corresponding static one by 80-90 μ s. The tangential stress on the hole boundary σ_{θ} is approximated by (7-9),

$$\sigma_{\theta} = E_{\theta} \cdot \frac{NF}{1+\nu} \quad (6)$$

where E_{θ} is Young's modulus along the boundary and a function of the angle θ . The comparison of σ_{θ} at about $t=100 \mu$ s is shown in Fig. 7. Although FEM gives slightly larger values than the photoelastic-coating analysis, the general trend is the same.

Carbon/Epoxy, Unidirectional, D/W = 26/50, $\phi = 0^{\circ}$

Since the elastic wave speed in the longitudinal direction is large, the reflected wave comes back before an incident strain reaches its constant value ϵ_0 . High-speed photographs in Fig. 8 were taken before the arrival of the reflected wave. Since the coating thickness is large, only qualitative discussion can be made. Note that the maximum fringe value on the hole boundary does not lie on the ends of the horizontal diameter and that fringe patterns are rather flat around the hole boundary.

Glass/Polyester, Plain-Woven Cloth, D/W = 26/50, $\phi = 45^{\circ}$

The directions of fibers and loading are different in this case. The fringes extend in the 45° or fiber direction as shown in Fig. 9. The comparison of fringe patterns and stress (strain) concentration factors are shown in Fig. 10. It should be noted that K_c is larger than K_s in this case. Both FEM and strain-gage results, K_c^{cal} and K_c^c are bounded by the photoelastic-coating results, K_c and K_c^s . It takes more than 110μ s for the stress concentration factors to reach its maximum because the elastic wave speed in the loading direction is relatively small.

Glass/Polyester, Unidirectional, D/W = 26/50, $\phi = 45^{\circ}$

A sequence of high-speed photos (Fig. 11) shows dynamic fracture. From this photos, we can know when, where, and in what direction dynamic fracture occurs. This gives quite a new information which other experimental methods cannot provide. The authors believe this experimental technique can be used in many other applications.

Glass/Polyester, Unidirectional, D/W = 10/50, $\phi = 0^{\circ}$ (Fig. 12)

These photos are supposed to be similar to those for an infinite plate.

Glass/Polyester, Unidirectional, D/W = 26/38.5, $\phi = 0^{\circ}$ (Fig. 13)

By the constraint of straight boundaries, the fringe patterns become similar to those for unidirectional carbon/epoxy specimens.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Photoelastic-coating technique utilizing a newly-constructed Cranz-Schardin camera of reflection type was developed to investigate dynamic strain or stress concentrations in composite strips with a circular hole in high-velocity tension. Four different kinds of composites in a very wide range of anisotropy were tested to study the effects of anisotropy, loading direction, and the (hole diameter/strip width) ratio on the dynamic stress (strain) concentration. Then photoelastic-coating results were compared with the results obtained by the strain-gage measurements and FEM analysis. To summarize the results, the maximum values of stress (strain) concentration factors and the corresponding times when these maximum values were obtained, are listed in Table 2. Strain-gage results K_c are almost bounded by the photoelastic-coating results K_{cmax} and K_{cmax}^{st} , and these three values are slightly smaller than FEM results K_{cmax}^{cal} . The corresponding static stress concentration factors K_c (calculated by FEM) are close to K_{cmax}^{cal} . As expected, the time τ_{max} increases as the elastic wave speed in the loading direction, c , decreases and also as the (hole diameter/strip width) ratio increases.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors acknowledge Asahi Fiber Glass Co. Ltd. and Toray Industries, Inc. for fabrication of composite specimens.

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Table 1 List of dynamic photoelastic-coating experiments.

(1) D/W=26/50

Composite System	Angle, ϕ		
	0°	90°	45°
G/P, PW	○	○	○
G/P, SUSW	○	○	○
G/P, UD	○*	×	○*
C/E, UD	○*	×	×

* $t_c=1.01, 3.01\text{mm}$, both

(2) G/P, UD, D/W: variable

D/W	
10/50	○
20/50	○
26/50	○
26/43.3=0.6	○
26/38.5=0.675	○
26/36=0.722	○

Table 2 Summary of the maximum stress concentration factors and the corresponding times when these maximum values were obtained.

Composite $\phi, D/W$	K_{cmax} (T_{cmax})	K_{smax} (T_{smax})	K_{gmax} (T_{gmax})	K_{calmax} (T_{calmax})	K_{st}
G/P, UD 0°, 26/50	5.44 (80)	5.87 (80)	5.56 (88)	6.14 (97)	6.23
G/P, SUSW 0°, 26/50	5.29 (95)	5.91 (95)	5.85 (98)	6.07 (104)	6.04
G/P, PW 0°, 26/50	4.42 (120)	5.52 (120)	5.43 (123)	5.41 (108)	5.26
G/P, PW 45°, 26/50	3.77 (125)	3.31 (125)	3.50 (127)	3.45 (131)	3.42

DECREASE OF $c \rightarrow$ INCREASE OF τ_{max}

Composite $\phi, D/W$	K_{cmax} (T_{cmax})	K_{smax} (T_{smax})	K_{gmax} (T_{gmax})	K_{calmax} (T_{calmax})	K_{st}
G/P, UD 0°, 26/50	5.44 (80)	5.87 (80)	5.56 (88)	6.14 (97)	6.23
G/P, UD 0°, 10/50	3.66 (75)	3.96 (75)	4.06 (85)	4.05 (95)	3.95
G/P, UD 0°, 20/50	4.61 (80)	4.97 (80)	5.08 (87)	5.11 (97)	5.08
G/P, UD 0°, 26/38.5	6.51 (105)	7.02 (105)	6.40 (106)	7.94 (105)	8.12

INCREASE OF D/W \rightarrow INCREASE OF τ_{max}

- S: LIGHT SOURCE
- D: DELAY GENERATOR
- FL: FIELD LENS
- P1: POLARIZER
- P2: ANALYZER
- Q1, Q2: QUARTER-WAVE PLATE
- C: 9-FRAME CAMERA
- PC: PHOTOELASTIC COATING
- T: TEST SPECIMEN

Fig. 1 Optical system of a Cranz-Schardin camera of reflection type.

Fig. 2 Specimen dimensions.

Fig. 3 Typical strain-gage results.
(glass/polyester, unidirectional,
D/W = 26/50, $\phi = 0^\circ$)

Fig. 4 A sequence of high-speed isochromatic-fringe patterns. (glass/polyester, unidirectional, $D/W = 26/50$, $\phi = 0^\circ$, $t_c = 1.01$ mm).

Fig. 5 Comparison of fringe patterns obtained by photoelastic-coating experiments and FEM analysis. (glass/polyester, unidirectional, $D/W = 26/50$, $\phi = 0^\circ$, $t_c = 1.01$ mm).

Fig. 6 Comparison of transient strain (stress) concentration factors. Two lines by photoelastic-coating analysis correspond to K (upper) and K' (lower), respectively. (glass/polyester, unidirectional, $D/W = 26/50$, $\phi = 0^\circ$).

Fig. 7 Tangential stress on the hole boundary. (glass/polyester, unidirectional, $D/W = 26/50$, $\phi = 0^\circ$).

Fig. 8 A sequence of high-speed isochromatic-fringe patterns. (carbon/epoxy, unidirectional, $D/W = 26/50$, $\phi = 0^\circ$, $t_c = 3.01 \text{ mm}$).

Fig. 9 A sequence of high-speed isochromatic-fringe patterns. (glass/polyester, plain-woven cloth, $D/W = 26/50$, $\phi = 45^\circ$, $t_c = 1.01 \text{ mm}$).

Fig. 10 Comparison of fringe patterns and strain (stress) concentration factors. (glass/polyester, plain-woven cloth, $D/W = 26/50$, $\phi = 45^\circ$).

Fig. 11 A sequence of high-speed isochromatic-fringe patterns. Dynamic fracture occurs. (glass/polyester, unidirectional, $D/W = 26/50$, $\phi = 45^\circ$, $t_c = 1.01 \text{ mm}$).

Fig. 12 A sequence of high-speed isochromatic-fringe patterns. (glass/polyester, unidirectional, $D/W = 10/50$, $\phi = 0^\circ$, $t_c = 1.01 \text{ mm}$).

Fig. 13 A sequence of high-speed isochromatic-fringe patterns. (glass/polyester, unidirectional, $D/W = 26/38.5$, $\phi = 0^\circ$, $t_c = 1.01 \text{ mm}$).